

Ternary complexes of copper-, nickel- and zinc(II) with some peptides and imidazoles : A potentiometric study

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Proton-ligand constants for two peptides (glycylalanine and glycylvaline) and three imidazoles (imidazole, 2-methylimidazole and 2-ethylimidazole), hydrolytic constants for three metal ions (Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}), stability constants for binary and ternary complexes of these metal ions and ligands have been determined by potentiometric method at 30° in 0.2 M NaClO_4 . The calculations have been made using the SCOGS computer programme. Stabilities of ternary complexes of Cu^{II} : (GA/GV) : ImH (1 : 1 : 1) with respect to different imidazoles have been evaluated. The observed order has been explained in terms of electronic and molecular structure of the alkyl substituents.

As a part of general programme of complex formation of transition metal ions¹ with peptides and imidazoles, we describe here the results of combined pH-metric and spectrophotometric investigations on the mixed ligand complex formation of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , and Zn^{II} with glycylalanine and glycylvaline as primary ligands (abbreviated hereafter as AH) and imidazoles, viz. imidazole (ImH), 2-methylimidazole (m-ImH) and 2-ethylimidazole (e-ImH) as secondary ligands (abbreviated hereafter as L) in aqueous solution at 30° at a fixed ionic strength (0.1 M NaClO_4). The dipeptides glycylalanine (GAH) and glycylvaline (GVH) contain three coordination sites, viz. amino, carboxylic and peptide groups. Dipeptides are known to show ambidentate² character in coordination with metal(II) with change in pH. Imidazoles are biologically important ligands involved in active sites of metalloenzymes as a part of histidine moiety³ and provide potential binding site for metal ions⁴.

Results and Discussion

Representative titration curves for the systems studied are given in Fig. 1. The parts of the titration curve at and above the pH value, where precipitation occurs have not been included for the calculation of the stability constants. A typical set of distribution curves for complex formation equilibria are given in Fig. 2. Proton-ligand constants, hydrolytic constants of M^{2+} ions, stability constants of binary complexes and ternary complexes are presented in Tables 1-4.

Protonation constants : Values of protonation constants along with earlier values^{1,5} are given in Table 1. The two peptides, viz. glycylalanine and glycylvaline show two replaceable protons. Imidazole, 2-methylimidazole and 2-ethylimidazole have only one replaceable proton each. The

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves : (1) acid only, (2) GAH, (3) ImH, (4) Cu^{II} . GA (1 : 1), (5) Cu^{II} : ImH (1 : 1) and (6) Cu^{II} . GA : ImH (1 : 1 : 1).

protonation constants of imidazole is less than that of 2-methylimidazole and ethylimidazole. This may be due to inductomeric effect. Since alkyl group has electron-releasing property, replacement of proton by an alkyl group at position-2 should allow flow of electrons to the pyrrole nitrogen and in turn to N-H bond, obviously causing an increase in protonation constant. Further, the electron-releasing properties of methyl and ethyl groups are almost similar

and they show the same values of the protonation constants.

Stability constants of complexes : The stability constants of 1 : 1 binary and 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes along with earlier reported values^{1,6} given in Tables 3 and 4 respectively, are in closer agreement.

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves : (1) GAH, (2) ImH⁺, (3) Cu-(GA)⁺, (4) Cu (Im)²⁺, (5) Cu (GA) (Im)⁺, (6) Cu (H₋₁GA), (7) Cu (H₋₁GA) (Im) and (8) F_{Cu2+}.

Table 1. Protonation constants of ligands

Ligand*	Log K ₁ ^H	log K ₂ ^H
GAH	8.28, 8.22 ^a , 8.19 ^a , 8.25 ^a	3.18, 3.14 ^a , 3.34 ^a
GVH	8.25, 8.23 ^a , 8.18 ^a	3.15 ^a , 3.15 ^a
ImH	7.12, 7.1 ^b	
m-ImH	8.10, 8.2 ^a	
e-ImH	8.10, 8.2 ^a	

*GAH = Glycylalanine; GVH = glycylvaline; ImH = imidazole; m-ImH = 2-methylimidazole; e-ImH = 2-ethylimidazole.

^aRef. 5. ^bRef. 1.

Table 2. Hydrolytic constants of M²⁺ (aq.) ions

	Ni	Cu	Zn
log K _M ^H	-8.10	-6.29	-7.89
log K _M ^{2H}	-16.87	-13.10	-14.80

Table 3. Stability constants of binary complexes

A/L	Ni	Cu	Zn
log K _{M(A)} ^M	GAH 4.21, 4.28 ^a	5.81, 5.74 ^a , 5.70 ^b , 5.79 ^c	4.10, 4.10 ^b
	GVH 4.28, 4.31 ^{a,c}	5.89, 5.77 ^a	4.20, 4.19 ^b
log K _{M(L)} ^M	ImH 2.83, 2.39 ^b , (2.78) ^{a,b}	4.12 (4.22) ^b , (4.20) ^a	2.53 (2.57) ^b , (2.48) ^{a,b}
log K _{M(L)} ^M	m-ImH 3.00 (3.96) ^{a,b}	5.28 (5.32) ^a	2.82 (2.83) ^{a,b}
	e-ImH 3.00 (3.96) ^{a,b}	5.28 (5.32) ^{a,b}	2.82 (2.83) ^{a,b}

^aRef. 1. ^bRef. 6. ^cRef. 5.

Table 4. Stability constants of ternary complexes

A	L	Cu		Ni		Zn	
		log β _{M(A)(L)} ^M	Δ log K _M	log β _{M(A)(L)} ^M	Δ log K _M	log β _{M(A)(L)} ^M	Δ log K _M
GAH	ImH	9.28	-0.58	6.15	-0.89	5.50	1.13
	m-ImH	10.19	-0.58	6.66	-0.55	6.19	-0.73
	e-ImH	10.19	-0.58	6.66	-0.55	6.19	-0.73
GVH	ImH	8.86	-1.16	6.06	-1.05	5.40	-1.33
	m-ImH	9.97	-0.98	6.48	-0.8	5.62	-1.40
	e-ImH	9.97	-0.98	6.48	-0.8	5.62	-1.40

Table 5. Visible band position for ternary complexes

System	λ _{max} (cm ⁻¹)
Cu : GAH : ImH (1 : 1 : 1)	15870
Cu : GAH : m-ImH (1 : 1 : 1)	15740
Cu : GAH : e-ImH (1 : 1 : 1)	15740
Cu : GVH : ImH (1 : 1 : 1)	16130
Cu : GVH : m-ImH (1 : 1 : 1)	16000
Cu : GVH : e-ImH (1 : 1 : 1)	16000

Binary complexes : The stability constant values for M^{II} : GVH are greater than those for M^{II} : GAH. Similarly, the stability constant values for M^{II} : m-ImH/e-ImH are greater than those of M^{II} : ImH. The trend of the stability constants is : m-ImH ≈ e-ImH > ImH. The log K values for substituted primary and secondary ligands from the steric considerations should be smaller than that for unsubstituted one. There is not much difference either in ligand basicity or the steric effect among the substituted imidazoles, both m-ImH and e-ImH therefore give nearly equal values for all metal ions. It is evident that the stability of binary M(A) and M(B) complexes under investigation follow the trend : Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II}. This is in accordance with expected value of stability of the complexes of these metal ions⁷.

Ternary complexes : The stability constants (log β_{MAL}^M) for ternary systems are given in Table 4. Since the complex formation equilibria and hydrolytic equilibria of the M²⁺ (aq.) ions are overlapping, the hydroxo species such as M(OH)⁺, M(OH)₂, M(A)(OH)⁻, M(B)(OH)⁺ have been considered in the complexation equilibria of ternary M(A)(L) systems. Only 1 : 1 : 1 ternary M : A : L mixture has been used in the study to ensure the exclusive formation of the simpler complex. Complex formation equilibria have been described on the basis of the species distribution and the representative distribution curves are presented in Fig. 2. The Δ log K_M values are negative in all these cases and the values are more negative in the case of substituted imidazoles. The values are more negative in case of Cu^{II} : GVH : m-/e-ImH system than Cu^{II} : GAH : m-/e-ImH system. This

is because of steric hindrance in the formation of the ternary complex due to the presence of the alkyl groups.

Considering the pK^H value of the ligands and the hydrolytic constants of the M^{2+} ions, the following species such as M^{2+} , AH , LH^+ , $M(OH)^+$, $M(OH)_2$, $M(A)^+$, $M(L)^{2+}$, $M(A)(L)^+$ and $M(H_{-1}A)(L)$ have been considered to exist in the complexation equilibria.

If the species distribution curves for Cu^{II} : GAH/GVH : ImH systems are considered the formation of ternary complex $Cu(A)(L)$ may be governed by the equations,

On the other hand, $Ni(A)(L)^+$ and $Zn(A)(L)^+$ complexes are formed as per the equations,

However, in the $Zn^{II}/AH/L$ systems, there are two additional equilibria, leading to the formation of mixed ligand $Zn(A)(L)^+$ complexes :

Stability constant with respect to imidazole : The formation constants of the metal imidazole (1 : 1) binary complex follow the order : $m\text{-ImH} \approx e\text{-ImH} > \text{ImH}$. As we pass from imidazole to 2-ethylimidazole, an increase in $\log K$ value is observed, which is due to increase in basicity of the ligands. From the steric considerations, the $\log K$ values in case of the complexes with substituted imidazoles should be smaller than that for imidazole complexes. The increase

in basicity in substituted imidazoles thus compensates for the negative contribution of the steric effect and further enhances the value of $\log K$ in all the cases. Among the substituted imidazoles, there is not much difference either in the ligand basicity or in the steric effect, so that both 2-methylimidazole and 2-ethylimidazole give almost similar $\log K$ values. The stability constants for $M(A)(L)^+$ 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complex show the same trend of variation as the binary complexes.

Stability constants in terms of divalent metal ions : The stability constants with respect to metal ions fall in the Irving-William order⁷ : $Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II}$. The higher values of $\log K$ in the case of the Cu^{II} chelates are due to Jahn-Teller effect.

Spectrophotometric study : Electronic spectra of the copper(II) binary and ternary systems, were recorded at different pH-values (Fig 3) and λ_{max} ($\approx 10 Dq$) values are tabulated in Table 5. The observed trend in λ_{max} is : $\text{ImH} > m\text{-ImH} \approx e\text{-ImH}$. The electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes in aqueous solution were recorded only at pH 7.0 by keeping the experimental conditions same as those for the potentiometric measurements. The spectral data of the Ni^{II} com-

Fig. 3 Visible absorption spectra for Cu^{II} GAH ImH (1 : 1 : 1) ternary system

Table 6 Visible spectral data of ternary nickel(II) complexes

Compd	ν_1 (cm^{-1})	ν_2 (cm^{-1})	ν_3 (cm^{-1})	$10 Dq$ (cm^{-1})	ν_2/ν_1	B (cm^{-1})	β
$[Ni^{II}(H_2O)_6]^{2+}$	9090	13890	25300	9090	1.53	794.66	0.771
Ni^{II} ImH (1 : 1)	9090	15260	25570	9090	1.67	907.00	0.880
Ni^{II} m-ImH (1 : 1)	9010	13750	25510	9010	1.52	815.33	0.791
Ni^{II} e-ImH (1 : 1)	9010	13750	25510	9010	1.52	815.33	0.791
Ni^{II} GAH (1 : 1)	1000	15870	25970	10000	1.58	789.33	0.766
Ni^{II} GAH ImH (1 : 1 : 1)	9950	16130	25700	9950	1.62	798.66	0.775
Ni^{II} GAH m-ImH (1 : 1 : 1)	10300	16300	26040	10300	1.58	762.67	0.740
Ni^{II} GAH e-ImH (1 : 1 : 1)	10300	16300	26040	10300	1.58	762.67	0.740
Ni^{II} GVH (1 : 1)	9840	15620	25900	9840	1.58	800.00	0.777
Ni^{II} GVH ImH (1 : 1 : 1)	9940	15870	25840	9940	1.59	792.67	0.769
Ni^{II} GVH m-ImH (1 : 1 : 1)	9890	16050	26110	9890	1.62	832.66	0.808
Ni^{II} GVH e-ImH (1 : 1 : 1)	9890	16050	26110	9890	1.62	832.66	0.808

plexes are presented in Table 6. The 10 Dq values follow the order of the ligands: $\text{ImH} < 2\text{-methylImH} \approx 2\text{-ethylImH}$. The order of the ligands may be explained in terms of electron-repelling group present in the respective ligands. The β (nephthauxetic ratio) value for all the nickel(II) complexes lie in the range 0.75–0.84, suggesting strong covalent character of the metal-ligand bond. Also, the ν_2/ν_1 values are as expected for the octahedral complexes. The ν_2 and ν_3 values occur at higher frequency for the ternary complexes. A near-linear correlation is observed between the 10 Dq values and $\log K$ values for the binary systems.

Experimental

All reagents used were of A.R. grade and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled CO_2 -free water. Metal ion solutions were standardized by usual procedures⁸.

pH was measured on a Systronics 335 pH-meter using a special glass electrode and a saturated calomel electrode. Temperature of the solution was controlled at 30°. The following sets (total volume 40 ml) of solutions were prepared: (i) 0.025 M perchloric acid + 0.1 M sodium perchlorate, (ii) 0.025 M perchloric acid + 0.00625 M primary ligands + 0.1 M sodium perchlorate, (iii) 0.025 M perchloric acid + 0.00625 M secondary ligand + 0.1 M sodium perchlorate, (iv) 0.025 M perchloric acid + 0.0625 M metal(II) perchlorate + 0.00625 M primary ligand + 0.1 M sodium perchlorate, (v) 0.025 M perchloric acid + 0.00625 M metal(II) perchlorate + 0.00625 M secondary ligand + 0.1 M sodium perchlorate, and (vi) 0.025 M perchloric acid + 0.00625 M metal(II) perchlorate + 0.00625 M primary ligand + 0.00625 M secondary ligand + 0.1 M sodium perchlorate. All sets of solution were titrated against 1.0 M sodium hydroxide.

The spectrophotometric determinations were carried out on a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cell in aqueous solution as a function of pH in the case of Cu^{II} binary and ternary systems, whereas in case of Ni^{II} systems the data were recorded only at pH 7.0.

Calculations: The stability constants may be written as

$$K_{\text{MGA/GV}}^{\text{M}} = \frac{\text{M}(\text{GA/GV})}{(\text{M})(\text{GAH/GVH})}$$

$$K_{\text{M(Im)}}^{\text{M}} = \frac{\text{M}(\text{Im})}{(\text{M})(\text{ImH})}$$

$$\beta_{(\text{MGA/GV})(\text{Im})}^{\text{M}} = \frac{\text{M}(\text{GA/GV})(\text{Im})}{(\text{M})(\text{GAH/GVH})(\text{ImH})}$$

The charges being omitted from metal ions for the sake of simplicity. Stability of ternary complexes MAL are generally characterised on the basis of $\Delta \log K_{\text{M}}^{\text{M}}$ values, calculated using the relation⁹,

$$\Delta \log K_{\text{M}}^{\text{M}} = \log \beta_{\text{M}(\text{GA/GV})(\text{Im})}^{\text{M}} - \log K_{\text{M}(\text{GA/GV})}^{\text{M}} - \log K_{\text{M}(\text{Im})}^{\text{M}}$$

The protonation constants of ligands and stability constants of binary complexes were determined by Calvin-Bjerrum technique¹⁰ as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹¹. The stability constants of the ternary complexes were evaluated using SCOGS computer programme¹².

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